

On the Determination of Solution Moment of a Solute

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Earp and Glasstone theory³ on the dielectric polarization of binary mixtures has been discussed theoretically to understand the merits of the proposed equation by Earp and Glasstone. An attempt is made to modify Earp and Glasstone method without violating the very purpose of their suggestions. Validity of the modified relation is discussed with the study of dielectric polarization of Phenol, Ethyl acetate and Chlorobenzene in benzene.

THE method of dielectric polarization measurements in binary mixtures of a polar solute in a polar/non-polar solvent is extensively adopted not only for studying the electrical aspects of molecular behaviour, but also for tracing the possible existences of molecular interaction and the extent of electronic perturbations by the influences of neighbouring molecules¹⁻³. Considering the case of a mixture of components X and Y, Earp and Glasstone³ pointed out the possibility of formation of additive compound XY, what is known as loose complex, in which a definite linkage is formed. The dioxane effect⁴⁻⁶ and the detailed study of molecular conformation of such loose complexes⁷⁻¹⁰ have led to understand the degree of electronic perturbation and the classification of solute-solvent interaction to some extent. The purpose of this paper is to explore further a simple approach to molecular polarization of a polar solute in a polar/non-polar solvent at infinite dilution.

Experimental

The apparatus and methods used were as previously described¹¹. Each compound was purified by standard methods immediately before its dipole moment was determined.

Theoretical Considerations :

Earp and Glasstone theory³ implies that the total polarization of a binary mixture, in general, varies linearly with the square of volume polarization and it was reasonably concluded that it indicates the absence of chemical interaction between the components of the solution^{9,12,13}. According to Earp and Glasstone, the molar polarization of mixtures can be expressed by the following expression.

$$P_{12} = A + B \left[\frac{\epsilon_{12} - 1}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \right]^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

where P_{12} is the molar polarization of the mixture, ϵ_{12} , the dielectric constant of the mixture and A and B are constants for a given solute and solvent,

the value of which, by considering the polarization of mixtures is a linear function of its excess of square of volume polarization over that of the solvent, can be shown as,

$$B = \frac{P_2 - P_1}{\left(\frac{\epsilon_2 - 1}{\epsilon_2 + 2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_1 + 2} \right)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

and

$$A = P_1 - B \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_1 + 2} \right)^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the dielectric constants of solvent and solute having molecular polarization P_1 and P_2 respectively. From these relations one can obtain for the molecular polarization of solution as

$$P_{12} = P_1 + \frac{(P_2 - P_1)(\epsilon_2 + 2)^2}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)} \left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon(5\epsilon_1 - 3\epsilon_{12} + 2\epsilon_{12}\epsilon_1)}{(\epsilon_{12} + 2)^2(5\epsilon_1 - 3\epsilon_2 + 2\epsilon_1\epsilon_2)} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

where $\Delta\epsilon = \epsilon_{12} - \epsilon_1$, the excess of dielectric constant of the mixture over that of the solvent. Under the assumption of an ideal mixture condition by keeping the molecular polarization of the solvent molecule invariant, equal to the value for the pure liquid, the apparent polarization of solute molecule can be easily computed.

In most cases Earp and Glasstone method (EGM) leads to higher values of molar polarization than that of the experimentally observed values using the relation¹⁴.

$$P_{12} = \frac{\epsilon_{12} - 1}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \cdot \frac{M_1 f_1 + M_2 f_2}{d_{12}} \quad \dots (5)$$

It implies that Earp and Glasstone theory needs some modifications. An attempt is made to modify their relation without violating the very purpose of Earp and Glasstone method.

Considering chemically non-interacting systems, it is well noted that the effective molar polarization P_{12} of dilute solution in polar/non-polar solvents

shows linearity to the excess volume polarization over that of the solvent. By adopting a similar procedure, the effective molar polarization of dilute binary mixtures may be expressed as

$$P_{12} = P_1 + \frac{(P_2 - P_1)(\epsilon_2 + 2)}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)} \left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

From the knowledge of concentration dependance of the apparent molar polarization for the solute, the molar polarization of the solute at infinite dilution can be obtained by extrapolation and the dipole moment μ (in Debye Unit) of the solute molecule can be computed from the usual expression.

$$\mu = 0.01281 \sqrt{(P_2 - R_D)T} \quad \dots (7)$$

where R_D is the molar refraction of the solute for the sodium D line and T is the temperature of measurement in degrees absolute.

Results and Discussion

With a view to examine the merits of the proposed equation, the study of dielectric polarization of Phenol, Ethyl acetate and Chlorobenzene in benzene, though studied earlier, has been undertaken. The results are given in Tables 1 to 3. The values of molecular polarization at infinite dilution and the dipole moment for the solutes studied here are reported in Table 4. To compare the dipole moment the values taken from the "Tables of Experimental dipole moments"¹⁵ are used.

It is well known that the dielectric constants of binary mixtures are not usually equal to the calculated average values¹⁶. The molar polarization of solute molecule in solvent usually increases at infinite dilution and this can be taken as an indication for the complexing tendency of solute molecule with solvent molecule. When there is absolutely no interaction between solute and solvent molecules, the curve ϵ_{12} vs f_2 , the mole fraction of solute should be linear. This leads to

$$P_{2\infty} = P_1 + (P_2 - P_1) \frac{\epsilon_2 + 2}{\epsilon_1 + 2} \quad \dots (8)$$

This is very similar with the empirical relation proposed for a system where strong or specific interactions are absent¹⁷. It is found that the range of validity of the reported relation for a quick determination of dipole moment in solution has got certain limitations over the range of dielectric constant of solute. This limitation may be due to the following reasons :

- (i) the opposing atmosphere of dipoles due to the non-symmetrically distributed interacting electrons about the atomic nuclei¹⁸,
- (ii) the intra and inter molecular interactions in the solute molecules,
- (iii) the existence of single and double ionic structure of molecules.

The critical examination of this equation¹⁹ shows that equation (8) is in unison with the above predictions.

TABLE 1—PHENOL-BENZENE BINARY SYSTEM

$\epsilon_1 = 2.2750$		$P_1 = 26.7450$ c.c.		$R_D = 28.14$			
$\epsilon_2 = 9.6940$		$P_2 = 72.7807$ c.c.		$T = 298K$			
$100f_2$	ϵ_{12}	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \right]$	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{(\epsilon_{12} + 2)f_2} \right]$	P_{12}		$P_{2\text{ app}}$	
				Modified EGM	EGM	Modified EGM	EGM
0.2460	2.2831	0.0019	0.772	26.888	26.954	82.79	111.66
0.4260	2.2895	0.0034	0.798	26.992	27.121	84.21	115.08
0.6720	2.2998	0.0057	0.849	27.159	27.388	88.37	122.41
0.7090	2.3012	0.0061	0.862	27.188	27.423	89.80	123.49
0.8150	2.3060	0.0072	0.883	27.268	27.548	90.86	125.94
0.9476	2.3120	0.0086	0.908	27.369	27.699	92.63	127.54

TABLE 2—ETHYL ACETATE-BENZENE BINARY SYSTEM

$\epsilon_1 = 2.2750$		$P_1 = 26.7450$ c.c.		$R_D = 17.61$			
$\epsilon_2 = 6.6721$		$P_2 = 52.8680$ c.c.		$T = 298K$			
$100f_2$	ϵ_{12}	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \right]$	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{(\epsilon_{12} + 2)f_2} \right]$	P_{12}		$P_{2\text{ app}}$	
				Modified EGM	EGM	Modified EGM	EGM
1.9891	2.3578	0.0190	0.955	27.723	29.092	75.93	94.47
3.0248	2.3909	0.0264	0.875	28.104	28.608	81.81	88.34
6.9236	2.5396	0.0583	0.842	29.747	30.786	70.11	85.11
8.6598	2.5988	0.0704	0.812	30.371	31.682	68.56	82.60

TABLE 3—CHLOROBENZENE-BENZENE BINARY SYSTEM

$\epsilon_1 = 2.2750$ $\epsilon_2 = 5.6212$		$P_1 = 26.7450$ c.c. $P_2 = 61.7880$ c.c.		$R_D = 32.85$ $T = 298K$			
$10f_2$	ϵ_{12}	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\epsilon_{12} + 2} \right]$	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{(\epsilon_{12} + 2)f_2} \right]$	P_{12} Modified EGM	EGM	$P_{2, app}$ Modified EGM	EGM
0.2758	2.3538	0.0180	0.655	28.181	28.625	79.02	94.92
0.6458	2.4378	0.0367	0.568	29.674	30.536	72.08	85.45
0.8991	2.4788	0.0454	0.541	30.368	31.414	69.92	82.39
1.1053	2.5027	0.0508	0.460	30.800	31.932	63.46	73.67
1.3662	2.5430	0.0590	0.432	31.454	32.768	61.22	70.83
1.6192	2.5692	0.0644	0.398	31.885	33.298	58.51	67.21

TABLE-4

Solute	$\left[\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{(\epsilon_{12} + 2)f_2} \right]_{f_2 \rightarrow 0}$	$P_{2, oc}$ c.c.	μ	μ other values from literature*
Phenol	0.74	80.47	1.60	1.60
Ethyl acetate	1.05	80.62	1.75	1.77
Chlorobenzene	0.73	85.06	1.59	1.58

* values are expressed in Debye units.
* Reference (15).

With a rough approximation, the modified relation explains Higashi equation²⁰, proposed for a quick determination of electric dipole moment of a molecule. According to Higashi,

$$\mu = S \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{f_2} \right)}_{f_2 \rightarrow 0} \quad \dots (9)$$

where S is a constant characteristic of the solvent. For benzene Higashi gave a value of 0.9) with a possible fluctuation of ± 0.10 e.s.u., With an assumption that at very low concentration $\epsilon_{12} + 2 \approx \epsilon_1 + 2$ and by neglecting $P_1 - R_D$, one can get,

$$S = 0.01281 \left[\frac{(P_2 - P_1)(\epsilon_2 + 2)}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(\epsilon_1 + 2)} T \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (10)$$

The characteristic values of S have been determined from the equation (10). The calculated values are 0.94 for Phenol, 0.77 for Ethyl acetate and 0.95 for Chlorobenzene and are more or less in close agreement with Higashi's proposed value 0.90 ± 0.10 .

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